

**ASSESSING THE EMERGENCY MEDICAL SERVICES UNIT OF DAVAO CITY
CENTRAL 911 PERFORMANCE BASED ON KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS
TOWARDS EMERGENCY AND DISASTER PREPAREDNESS**

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This research aims to assess the performance of the Davao City Central 911 EMS unit based on key performance indicators (KPIs) regarding emergency and disaster preparedness. Researchers conducted a pilot test on 30 selected EMS personnel, followed by an actual research survey on another 100. The study used a 45-item questionnaire to assess three KPIs: response time, workplace safety, and team coordination. Data collection occurred on-site through survey questionnaires and Google Forms. The results revealed that route accessibility, under the response time, tended to fall outside the average mean of 3.8740, with a standard deviation of .74342. This indicates that route accessibility significantly impacts response times. Therefore, ensuring efficient routes is critical to meet response time targets consistently. This means that it is relevant that their response time would improve more by reducing travel time in collaboration with other agencies, such as the city transport and traffic management office, and by consistently providing traffic and road accessibility information.

On the other hand, each component of workplace safety shows $PI = 1.7500$, $PCE = 1.3996$, and $SCB = 1.7206$. This indicates that this KPI has a very low influence on the level of performance of the EMS unit.; however, this still accounts for measures to promote safety. Therefore, this suggests that following the rules, work processes, and safety regulations is necessary to avoid jeopardizing the health of oneself, the patient, and the members of the team. Moreover, the mean for leadership and task management is 4.5 under team coordination, while the mean for teamwork is 4.4. The average score across these areas falls between 4.4 and 4.5, indicating very high performance in team coordination. Moreover, the standard deviation across these components falls between 0.6 and 0.8, indicating that the data points of this KPI are clustered

closer to the mean (4.4-4.5). It suggests high consistency in team coordination ratings, with most scores falling within a narrow range of the average.

The KPIs significantly influence the performance of EMS personnel. However, only the response time and the team coordination are substantial, which means these are the KPIs that can affect the EMS's overall performance during emergencies and disasters. The results of this study indicate that the key performance indicators (KPIs) significantly influence the performance of emergency medical service (EMS) personnel. However, only the response time and the team coordination are substantial, which means these are the KPIs that can affect the EMS's overall performance during emergencies and disasters.

Keywords: *Emergency Medical Service (EMS), Key Performance Indicator (KPI), correlational design, Davao City Central 911*